

from 1 780 and 1 750 cm^{-1} (free ligand) to $\sim 1 650$ and 1 620 cm^{-1} respectively, in the spectra of the complexes. The coordination via oxygen would give rise to a large difference in the fundamental stretching frequencies of the two carbonyl groups and one band would be shifted far more than the other by metal ion coordination. The fact that the frequencies of the two bands are lowered by an equivalent amount on coordination, suggests that the coordination occurred through nitrogen. A strong band at 3 300 cm^{-1} due to NH of imide changed into a band of negligible intensity in the spectra of their salts, indicates the deprotonation of imide group. This negative shift may be due to the mass effect⁹. The stretching frequency at 1 470 cm^{-1} due to C-N in the spectra of imides also shifted to $\sim 1 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes, indicating thereby the coordination of the imide ion with the metal ion⁴.

The characteristic ring vibrations of heterocyclic bases (terpyridyl) in the range 1 600–1 450 cm^{-1} generally show significant changes on complexation⁵ which could not be distinguished because of mixing or overlapping with C=O and C-N stretching bands in the complexes 1–4. The in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformation modes in these cases observed near 500 and 700 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the free ligand undergo a positive shift in the complexes which is usual for coordination through nitrogen⁵. The absence of the bands due to ν_{OH} ruled out the possibility of formation of solvated complex, i.e. $[\text{MN}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ or $[\text{MN}_6(\text{EtOH})]$.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra: The magnetic moment values of the nickel(II) complexes lie in the range 2.60–2.70 B.M. at room temperature. The values are lower than that expected for nickel(II) complexes⁶, but a few such observations are available at present^{7,8}. The magnetic moment values of cobalt(II) complexes are in the range 3.99–4.12 B.M. at room temperature. These values are considerably lower than that predicted for tetrahedral (4.40–4.87 B.M.) or octahedral (4.70–5.20 B.M.) complexes at room temperature^{9,10}.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes in dimethylformamide showed four bands in the range 8 100–8 700 (ν_1), 10 200–11 000 (ν_2), 14 500–16 000 (ν_3), 22 500–23 500 (ν_4) cm^{-1} , while cobalt(II) complexes in dimethylsulphoxide gave three bands in the range 9 200–10 650 (ν_1), 16 800–17 500 (ν_2) and 22 200–23 250 (ν_3) cm^{-1} . The presence of these bands at nearly the same positions was also observed in the spectra of the solid compounds, which indicated no dissociation of the complexes in solution and also not identifying them as polymeric solids with coordination number six. The four- or six-coordinated complexes of these metal ions do not give the bands in this range¹¹. However, these spectral bands resemble the spectra of five-coordinate complexes¹² whose structures have been established by X-ray measurements.

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Possible Different Behaviour of 4,4'-(4,4'-Biphenylenebisazo)-di(2-hydroxyacetophenone) in its Copper(II), Zinc(II) Iron(II), Iron(III) and Dioxouranium(VI) Chelates

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WE have the properties of polychelates derived by polymerising monomeric symmetric tetra-functioning ligands through metal ion¹. Here, in an attempt to prepare such polychelates of 4,4'-(4,4'-biphenylenebisazo)-di(2-hydroxyacetophenone) (L), we have obtained such polychelates for Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} gives dinuclear chelate of the formula $\text{Cu}_2\text{L}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_6$, while mononuclear chelates for UO_2^{II} and Zn^{II} . In the first case the polychelates have been obtained by polymerisation of L through metal ion in which L is tetra-functioning. In the second case L is tetra-functioning without any further polymerisation while in the last case it is bifunctioning. The preparation of the ligand and all the physicochemical measurements were made as described earlier².

Preparation of complexes: To a refluxing ligand solution (2.5 mmol in 80 ml DMF), a well stirred metal salt solution (2.5 mmol in 60 ml DMF) was added followed by sodium acetate (~ 2.0 g) and the resulting mixture was allowed to reflux for 3 h. The complexes thus obtained were filtered and washed with hot DMF, hot water and ethanol and dried at 40°.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the chelates are presented in Table 1. The Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} chelates suggest 1 : {

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Specific conductivity $\times 10^6 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff}^* B.M.
	M	N		
$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$	—	11.58 (11.71)	15.5	—
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4)(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	15.40 (15.22)	9.95 (10.05)	6.1	1.97
$\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	10.08 (9.84)	9.80 (9.86)	8.5	Ferromag.
$\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4)(\text{OH}_2\text{COO}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	9.03 (9.17)	9.08 (9.19)	9.7	9.98
$\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4)_2$	18.83 (19.44)	9.00 (9.16)	0.7	1.31
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	6.25 (6.20)	10.45 (10.61)	3.7	Diamag.

* At 301 K.

metal-ligand stoichiometry. The Cu^{II} chelate shows 2 : 1 metal-ligand ratio while the UO_2^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates reveal 1 : 2 ratio. The low values of specific conductances of all the chelates suggest their non-ionic nature.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the ligand show strong absorption band at $22\,222 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder at $25\,641 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ligand then shows continuous decrease upto $14\,285 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ after which there is practically no absorption. The former band may be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, while the latter may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition³. The large high energy shift compared to azobenzene may be due to the presence of extensive conjugation in the ligand⁴.

The reflectance spectra of the Zn^{II} complex show a strong band centered around $20\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be due to ligand absorption. As expected it is diamagnetic in nature. The Cu^{II} chelate shows very strong absorption centered at $20\,408 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with some sign of structure at $10\,100$, $11\,235$ and $13\,333 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The strong absorption may be due to ligand $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The observed weak shoulders may be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, considering tetragonally distorted structure of the chelate^{5,6}. The magnetic moment (1.97 B.M.) of the chelate is consistent with the presence of one unpaired electron.

The Fe^{II} spectra show two bands, the high energy band centered around $22\,222 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to ligand band while the low energy band with structures at $10\,000$, $8\,930$ and $8\,368 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may presumably contain $d-d$ transitions. The first two transitions may be due to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ for an octahedral iron(II)⁷, and the low energy band may be due to presence of low symmetry ligand field component⁸. Because of the highly ferromagnetic behaviour of the chelate, it was not possible to measure its magnetic moment with reasonable accuracy. Electronic spectra of the Fe^{III} chelate is comparable with the ligand spectra except that the high energy band is little shifted to low energy side. The spectrum is not well resolved and it is rather difficult to obtain any assignments. High magnetic

moment (9.98 B.M.) of the chelate indicates its ferromagnetic nature.

The reflectance spectra of UO_2^{II} chelates show a band at $18\,867 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ligand absorption. The chelate is found to be paramagnetic with magnetic moment of 1.31 B.M. This behaviour is not unknown and may be due to the presence of magnetic interaction which mix excited state into the zero field ground state⁹.

The ligand shows a medium broad band in the range $3\,300-3\,400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be due to ν_{OH} of the phenolic group¹. All chelates also show this band. This may be due to ν_{OH} of the phenolic group or it may be due to the presence of coordinated water. The ligand show strong bands at $1\,640$ ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and $1\,600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{N}=\text{N}$). The former band shows positive shift ($\Delta\nu=42 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggesting oxygen coordination of the ketonic group. A strong phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$ vibration present at $1\,125 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand is observed at higher energy ($\Delta\nu=25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in all the chelates. This suggests the oxygen coordination of the phenolic- OH^{10} . The Cu^{II} chelate shows bands at $1\,325$ and 840 cm^{-1} which may be due to stretching of nitrate-group¹¹. The bands at $1\,425$ and $1\,604 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the Fe^{II} chelate suggest the presence of monocoordinated acetate¹².

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Investigations on Reactions of Molybdenum(v) Complexes in Presence of 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole in Aqueous and Non-aqueous Media

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STABILITY, structure and bonding in the 'oxometal ions' species are greatly influenced by anionic environment and the nature of the donor atoms of the other ligands¹⁻⁴. In the present communication, we describe the isolation and characterisation of some oxomolybdate(v) bromo complexes with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (Pybmz).

Experimental

The ligand (Pybmz) was prepared according to the literature procedure⁵. All the other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of complexes :

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazolinoxopentabromomolybdate(v), $PybmzH_2[MoOBr_5]$: Molybdenum trioxide (~0.9 g) was reduced with boiling 48%

hydrobromic acid and to it Pybmz (0.6 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of the same acid was added with stirring. A yellow crystalline complex separated on cooling the mixture to room temperature. The solid was filtered, washed with 48% hydrobromic acid and dried under reduced pressure over solid KOH.

Oxotribromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(v), $[MoOBr_3.Pybmz]$: PybmzH₂[MoOBr₃] (~0.6 g) was refluxed with dry ethanol (10 ml) for 1 h. The resulting brick-red crystalline solid was filtered and dried under reduced pressure.

A yellow crystalline compound of the same composition was obtained by refluxing PybmzH₂[MoOBr₃] (0.6 g) with acetonitrile (15 ml) for 2 h. The product was filtered, washed with acetonitrile and dried under reduced pressure.

Oxo-μ-oxotetrabromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(v), $[Mo_2O_8Br_4(Pybmz)_2]$: A mixture of ammonium oxopentabromomolybdate (1.0 g) and dry ethanol (20 ml) was stirred for 10 min and filtered. An ethanolic solution of Pybmz (0.6 g) was then added to the filtrate. The resulting pink solid was filtered, washed with dry ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Oxo-μ-dioxobromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(v), $[Mo_2O_4Br_2(Pybmz)_2]$: PybmzH₂[MoOBr₃] (~0.8 g) was gently boiled with water (10 ml) for 15 min. The resulting brick-red solid was filtered, washed with cold water and dried under reduced pressure over solid KOH.

Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically as molybdenum trioxide⁶, bromide as silver bromide⁷, and nitrogen estimated by Dumas' method. The oxidation number of molybdenum was determined by titration with ceric sulphate⁸. Room temperature (30 ± 2°) magnetic moments values were determined by Gouy method. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra (in 9 M HBr, ethanol and acetonitrile) were recorded with a Varian 634 spectrophotometer. The results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data of PybmzH₂[MoOBr] in aqueous medium indicate extensive hydrolysis and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Oxidation number (z)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Λ_M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	Mo	Br	N			
PybmzH ₂ [MoOBr ₃]	13.63 (13.54)	56.59 (56.39)	6.04 (5.92)	5.12	1.86	—
[MoOBr ₃ .Pybmz] brick-red	18.02 (17.89)	44.03 (43.84)	8.03 (7.68)	5.09	1.53	18.47
[MoOBr ₃ .Pybmz] yellow	18.47 (17.89)	43.79 (43.84)	8.00 (7.68)	4.93	1.54	15.68
[Mo ₂ O ₈ Br ₄ (Pybmz) ₂]	20.45 (20.12)	33.65 (33.52)	9.20 (8.80)	4.81	1.25	18.00
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₂ (Pybmz) ₂]	26.32 (26.29)	21.92 (21.89)	11.72 (11.51)	4.97	Diamag.	10.94